

PORE-SCALE EVALUATION OF ENHANCED MIXING WITHIN PREFERENTIAL TRANSPORT ZONES

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ABSTRACT

A prerequisite to determining risk from a subsurface contaminant plume is to determine chemical concentrations down gradient from the source zone. For a conservative contaminant, down gradient concentrations depend on the initial source zone concentrations and the extent to which the contaminant mixes (i.e., dilutes) with the surrounding groundwater. For a (bio)reactive contaminant, down gradient concentrations also depend on the rate of reaction; this can be governed by the rate that the contaminant mixes with other substrates and the reaction rate constant. In this work we examine the effect of a high conductivity preferential flow zone on contaminant mixing and reaction at the pore scale. Two reactive substrates are introduced into a network of pores via two separate and parallel fluid streams. The substrates mix within the porous media via transverse dispersion and react. The lattice-Boltzmann (LB) method is used to solve for interstitial pore velocities. Reactive transport is simulated by combining pore velocities from the LB model with a reactive transport finite-volume model (FVM). The extent of mixing and reaction is quantified by evaluating product formation rates from the two substrates. Results from the LB-FVM simulations indicated that (i) the amount of product formed can be 40-50% higher due to flow focusing in the preferential flow zone, (ii) the amount of enhancement depends on the length and width of the preferential flow zone, and (iii) the bi-molecular reaction rate can have an effect on the total amount of product formed. Results are compared with an analytical solution developed for flow focusing scenarios at the continuum scale and with reactive fluorescent micro-model experiments which were conducted utilizing an identical porous media configuration to the base preferential mixing scenario evaluated utilizing the LB-FVM. This study suggests that flow focusing can significantly affect the overall extent of mixing and reaction in groundwater flow, and hence may need to be considered when evaluating reactive transport.

1. INTRODUCTION

A prerequisite to determining risk from a subsurface contaminant plume is to determine chemical concentrations down gradient from the source zone. For conservative contaminants (non-sorbing and non-reacting), the only viable mechanism to reduce concentrations is by dilution of the contaminant plume with the surrounding ground water. For (bio)reactive contaminants, degradation is controlled by the extent of mixing of substrates and the reaction rate. For some cases, natural attenuation is sufficient to control the spread and hence risk of a contaminant plume. In other cases, active stimulation of biological degradation or chemically induced oxidation of source zones are important remediation strategies. A key factor for many effective remediation strategies is efficient mixing of the contaminant with the appropriate reactants, and in the case of biological degradation, trace nutrients. As a precondition for degradation, the reactants must occupy the same parcel of fluid, thereby allowing the reactants to interact and collide at the molecular level. When groundwater contamination is from a persistent source, the pseudo steady state process of mixing is controlled by transverse dispersion. A notable exception to transverse dispersion controlled mixing is when compounds have differing retardation coefficients (differing affinities for sorption to the porous media). This process is the so called *chromatographic effect* or *traveling wave* and was shown by Oya and Valocchi [1998] to be a dominant mechanism for mixing between compounds of differing retardation coefficients. Excluding this notable exception, mixing in the subsurface is controlled by transverse dispersion.

At the field scale, dispersion is typically quantified by injecting a tracer at an injection well and then (i) measuring a down gradient breakthrough profile or transverse concentration profile or (ii) pumping the same well to extract groundwater and the tracer [Fetter 1993]. The dispersion coefficient is then determined by adjusting velocity and dispersion to obtain agreement between model and measured concentration breakthrough profiles. The measured dispersion coefficient is the so called macro-dispersion coefficient. Utilizing the measured dispersion coefficient provides good estimates of non-reactive chemical concentrations at receptor wells, but has been shown to significantly over predicts chemical transformation rates for reactive compounds. This occurs because the measured dispersion coefficient combines the effects of *mixing* and *spreading* [Jose and Cirpka 2004]. To illustrate the difference between mixing (dilution) and spreading, consider the following example; two fluid parcels initially occupy adjacent but separate regions in an aquifer. Reaction can only occur when the molecules of the two parcels are mixed; in the absence of sorption, this mixing process is controlled by molecular diffusion. As the two fluid parcels are transported through the aquifer they undergo stretching and deformation of their original shape due to velocity variations and divergence of stream tubes. The inter facial area between the parcels can increase through this process of spreading; however, the two parcels will remain separate and will not mix without the aid of molecular diffusion.

In an attempt to better quantify mixing, Jose and Cirpka [2004] utilized multiple “point” measurements to quantify break through profiles of a fluorescent conservative tracer.

Jose and Cirpka measured concentration break through at several planes within their packed sand column by using eight individual point measurements per cross section plane. Utilizing this approach, they demonstrated that dispersion coefficients estimated by considering an “averaged” concentration break through profile overestimated measurements of dispersion from the individual point measurements. Comparison of reactive experiments with model predictions based on the point dispersion measurements resulted in excellent fit at early time, but over predicted experimental results at later time. The authors contributed this effect to weak rate limited sorption.

In a pore scale study, Cao and Kitanidis [1998] found that dilution was enhanced at the necks of pores where stream lines converged. The convergence of stream tubes result in the width of the stream tube decreasing thereby enhancing the effect of molecular diffusion. This concept is commonly employed in microfluidics to mix substrates under laminar flow conditions. To quantify this enhancement, consider the time scale of transverse dispersion: $\tau_{D_T} \equiv l^2/D_T$ where l is the transverse length scale of heterogeneity and D_T is the transverse dispersion coefficient. When stream tubes converge, the transverse length l decreases thereby decreasing τ_{D_T} at the rate l^2 . Confirming this concept, Cirpka and Kitanidis [2002] demonstrated that focusing of the flow field in higher conductivity regions lead to increased dispersivity. As such, it is not so much the absolute value of the conductivity but rather the contrast in conductivity with the surrounding region.

In a recent paper, Werth et al. [2006] derived expressions to quantify the effect continuum flow focusing has on enhancing mixing in high conductivity preferential flow zones. Werth et al. found that mixing is enhanced at a rate proportional to

$$MF = \sqrt{\frac{D_i L_i n_i h_{tot} Q_{rel}}{D_m L_{tot} n_m h_i} + 1} - \frac{L_i}{L_{tot}} \quad (1)$$

where MF is the mixing enhancement factor, i refers to the high permeability inclusion within the aquifer matrix m , L is length, n is porosity, h is the height of the aquifer, Q_{rel} is the ratio of flow through the inclusion to total flow, Q_i/Q_{tot} . In agreement with the findings by Cirpka and Kitanidis, this equation indicates that the greater the flow focusing within a high permeability flow matrix, the greater the mixing enhancement.

In most of the experimental studies focused on evaluating non-linear reactions in porous media [Jose and Cirpka, 2004; Gramling et al., 2002; Raje and Kapoor, 2000], effective dispersion coefficients were determined by injecting conservative solutes as a plug into the porous media followed by measuring the concentration break through profiles at a point or plane down gradient. This approach makes it difficult to separate the effects of mixing from spreading and stretching of a plume. In our work we separate the effects of mixing and spreading by measuring transverse concentration profiles at steady state. This approach replicates pseudo-steady state field scenarios where contaminant plumes approach a balance between degradation rates and source zone input. By evaluating

steady state transport, we eliminate stretching due to variations in the flow field and hence are better able to separate the effects of mixing from stretching.

A better understanding of mixing enhancement can be an essential tool for designing effective remediation strategies. As discussed, a common limitation in many remediation strategies is effective mixing of the limiting substrate with the contaminant plume. Strategies which focus flow in higher conductivity regions can benefit from enhanced mixing of supplied substrates (e.g. injection of a limiting electron donor) with the contaminant plume, thereby limiting the overall spread, and hence risk from the contaminant.

1.1. Governing Equations. To evaluate the effects of non-linear bi-molecular chemical reaction on chemical transport in porous media, we focus our work on the following non-reversible elementary chemical reaction:

The molar concentrations [mol/L] of A, B, and C can be described as follows for a well mixed batch scenario:

$$\frac{d[A]}{dt} = \frac{d[B]}{dt} = -\frac{d[C]}{dt} = -k[A][B] \quad (3)$$

where t is time, and k is the intrinsic reaction rate [$\text{mol}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$]. The general form of the equations describing macroscopic solute transport in porous medium in two dimension can be written as:

$$n \frac{\partial(C_i)}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(nD \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(nD \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial y} \right) - \frac{\partial(nV_x C_i)}{\partial x} - knC_A C_B \quad i = A, B \quad (4)$$

$$n \frac{\partial(C_C)}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(nD \frac{\partial C_C}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(nD \frac{\partial C_C}{\partial y} \right) - \frac{\partial(nV_x C_C)}{\partial x} + knC_A C_B \quad (5)$$

Here, n denotes porosity [-], D is the dispersion tensor [$\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$], and V_x is the average linear velocity [cm s^{-1}]. The average linear velocity, porosity, and dispersion coefficients may vary in space.

2. METHODS

To better understand the fundamental mechanisms controlling flow focusing and enhanced mixing, we focus this paper on pore-scale reactive transport. This approach is attractive because the only inputs are porous media structure, a pressure gradient and molecular diffusion. By directly up-scaling pore-scale simulations, we directly evaluate transverse dispersion without having to make any assumptions about the empirical nature of the dispersion coefficient.

In both the pore-scale simulations and micro-model experiments we evaluate the following system. Two reactive substrates are introduced into a network of pores via two separate and parallel fluid streams (Figure 1). The substrates mix within the porous media via transverse dispersion and react. To model pore-scale reactive transport we utilize the lattice-Boltzmann (LB) method to solve for interstitial pore velocities. Reactive transport is simulated by combining pore velocities from the LB model with a reactive transport finite-volume model (FVM).

FIGURE 1. Schematic illustrating preferential flow focusing. The base porous media consists of $300\mu\text{m}$ cylinders. The low permeability region includes smaller $120\mu\text{m}$ cylinders in the interstitial voids of the base porous media.

2.1. Lattice-Boltzmann Finite Volume Method. The LB method is a kinetic based theory for modeling momentum and solute transport with complex boundary conditions [Knutson et al. 2001]. No-slip boundary conditions are imposed at all soil grains via a bounce-back boundary condition. Particles which move from a water node to a solid porous media node are bounced-back along the opposite vector in which they came (opposite direction, same speed). For Reynolds numbers less than 80, Koch and Ladd [1997] demonstrated that the error for bounce back conditions was less than 3% when separation distances between solid surfaces (no slip surfaces) were 10 nodes or greater.

At the inlet and outlet, fluid pressure is specified such that the resulting average velocity (Darcy velocity) is the same as the velocity in the experimental setup. The node spacing of the LB simulation is set to $5 \mu m$.

2.1.1. Reactive Transport. The LB method solves for the steady state fluid velocity at each node within the flow network. The velocity profile calculated from the LB method is used as input for a finite volume transport code in which inlet boundary conditions and outlet boundary conditions (BC) are defined to represent the conditions of the micro-model experiments. The inlet BC is defined as $C_{in} = B_o$ for the top half of the inlet flow boundary and as $C_{in} = A_o$ for the bottom half of the inlet flow boundary (Figure 1). The outlet BC is defined as pure advection: $(\frac{dC}{dx}) = 0$. For each nodal location, the flux into and the flux out of the node is evaluated utilizing a centered finite difference approach; the flux is evaluated by discretizing the advective dispersive flux equation: $F = UC - D\frac{dC}{dx}$ where the velocity U is known for each node based on the output from the LB simulation. The boundary conditions for each soil grain are handled by setting the flux into each face of the soil grain as zero. Reactive transport is evaluated via a pseudo-Newton Raphson approach in which the reaction term, see equations (4) and (5), is simulated as a second order bi-molecular reaction: $\frac{dC}{dt} = k[C_a][C_b]$.

2.1.2. REV Averaging. To determine up-scaled parameters from the LB-FVM simulation, the following approach is used. To determine extent of mixing, the mass of product C is calculated with distance by summing concentrations of compound C over the cross sectional area. Mass is calculated using a moving average approach where the total mass over a unit strip extending from $x - \frac{l_{rev}}{2}$ to $x + \frac{l_{rev}}{2}$ is calculated; l_{rev} is calculated as the distance from the center of one cylinder to the center of the adjacent cylinder. The total mass is normalized by l_{rev} and plotted versus longitudinal distance. This approach meets the criteria outlined by Bear [1972] for a REV.

2.2. Micro-model Fabrication. Micromodels have been utilized extensively in the literature to evaluate mixing within microfluidic channels [Wang et al., 2002; He et al., 2001; Johnson et al., 2002; Mengeaud et al., 2002; Munson and Yager, 2004]. Micro-models have been demonstrated to be an effective tool for measuring molecular diffusion coefficients [Kamholz and Yager, 2001; Kamholz et al., 1999, 2001]. In this work, micro-models are fabricated from a silicon substrate layer in a process similar to that used in fabrication of computer chips.

To create the high resolution micromodels used in this work, an initial porous media network is designed utilizing a computer CAD program. The digital image is transferred to a quartz plate mask before it is transferred to the silicon wafer. The quartz plate mask can be reused multiple times so that the same micro-model template can be reproduced precisely. To transfer the image from the mask to the silicon wafer substrate, the silicon wafer is coated with a photoresist (PR) polymer (Figure 2). The quartz mask is placed directly above (in contact with) the PR layer on the silicon wafer and is exposed to UV light. The cross linking in the PR layer is weakened by exposure to UV light; the

resulting areas that are exposed (e.g. areas not covered by the image on the mask) are weakened and are removed utilizing a developer. The exposed areas of the silicon wafer are etched using plasma generated from an ICP-DRIE. The ICP-DRIE etching of silicon is highly anisotropic, etching vertical side walls with uniform flat bottoms. The result is orthogonal flow channels of uniform depth. The remaining PR is removed from the silicon wafer utilizing heated PR stripper. Sealed flow channels are created by anodically bonding thin Pyrex[®] glass to the silicon wafer. The resulting product is a precise fabrication of any 2D micro model flow network with accuracies on the order of microns.

FIGURE 2. Schematic illustration of micro-model fabrication flow chart

2.2.1. Micro model Visualization. To quantify chemical concentrations within the micro-models, epifluorescent microscopy is used to quantify fluorescent intensities which are related to concentrations through a calibration curve. A Nikon Epiphot 200 microscope with a Prior motorized stage is used to capture steady-state fluorescent images which are then montaged together to form a single image capturing the entire mixing zone region. A total of 40+ images are captured to form each single montaged image.

In all the experiments, the fluorophore Oregon Green Bapta 488 (OG5N) in the Hexapotassium salt form is used (Invitrogen INC.). OG5N reacts with Ca²⁺ in a 1:1 stoichiometric ratio to form a fluorescent product. OG5N in the unbound form (e.g. before binding with Ca²⁺) has a very low background intensity which increases several fold once bound with Ca. To measure the molecular diffusion coefficient of bound OG5N, a procedure similar to Kamholz et al. [2001] was used. To evaluate reactive transport, Ca and OG5N are introduced via two separate and parallel fluid streams into the micro-models. The chemicals mix within the porous media due to transverse dispersion and react. Evaluating mixing by measuring product formation is advantageous because product can only be formed once the chemicals mix. The reaction rate for OG5N and Ca is quite fast and

FIGURE 3. Large-scale LB-FVM flow focusing simulation showing product C being formed along the mixing interface. This simulation represents an “inlet” flow focusing scenario where lower permeability regions above and below the centerline focus flow towards the mixing interface

can be considered instantaneous. As a result, product formation is directly related to mixing of the substrates.

2.3. Pore Geometries Evaluated. In this work, the effect of preferential focusing on mixing enhancement is studied. A total of seven (7) porous media configurations are evaluated in this report. The base case (1) consists of an isotropic homogeneous array of $300\mu\text{m}$ cylinders with $40\mu\text{m}$ pore throats. Flow focused models are created by adding $120\mu\text{m}$ cylinders to the interstitial pore space between the base array of cylinders (Figure 1). To evaluate flow focusing location on mixing, an *inlet* (2) flow focusing scenario (see Figure 3) and three *middle* flow focusing scenarios, short (3), medium (4) and long (5), are evaluated. For the middle flow focusing scenarios, the focusing region is moved down gradient relative to the inlet scenario. The effect of inclusion width was evaluated by creating a “narrow” (6) inclusion networks. The final configuration, (7), consists of an “extra focused” scenario where the secondary grains are $135\mu\text{m}$ instead of $120\mu\text{m}$; the larger grains result in a larger percentage of flow being focused toward the higher permeability inclusion. Large scale simulations identical to the micro-model experiments were also conducted.

The effect of intrinsic reaction rate on extent of product formation was also evaluated. Reaction rates ranging from $k_{eff} = 5 \times 10^3 \mu\text{M}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$ through $k_{eff} = 5 \times 10^{-3} \mu\text{M}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$ were evaluated.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the present study, we systematically evaluate the effects of preferential flow focusing geometry and intrinsic reaction rate on bi-molecular chemical reactions within porous media. Figure 3 shows product formation of solute “C” within a preferential flow focusing model. Solutes A and B are introduced on the left hand side at inlet concentrations $A_o = B_o = 30\mu\text{M}$. The product “C” forms along the mixing interface due to transverse dispersion. Figure 3 shows that the plume experiences a rapid expansion as the flow leaves the flow focused zone.

FIGURE 4. Mass calculated from LB-FVM simulations of seven flow regimes is plotted as a function of distance. Inlet preferential mixing refers to the enhanced mixing zone being located at the inlet. Middle preferential mixing refers to the enhanced mixing zone being located downstream from the inlet. Three lengths, short, medium and long, of the “middle” enhanced mixing zone scenario are evaluated.

3.1. LB-FVM Results. Following the procedure outlined in Methods section 2.1.2, the mass of product formed is calculated as a function of longitudinal distance by integrating product concentration over the width of the product plume. Figure 4 shows product mass versus distance for 7 different flow configurations. The mass of product formed in all preferential mixing scenarios exceed product formation for the base homogeneous case. Even considering that the residence time is reduced in each of the preferential flow scenarios (same darcy flow, lower porosity hence shorter resident time) compared to the base case, product formation rates are greater. Figure 4 shows that the longer flow is focused in the higher conductivity region, the greater the enhancement to mixing and overall production. This is in agreement with the analytical solution (eq. 1) derived by Werth et al. [2006] for continuum flow focusing. Also, Figure 4 shows that for regimes of identical length (assuming a fast reaction rate), their longitudinal location does not play a role in the overall mixing enhancement. The “narrow” simulation indicates that reduced inclusion width results in less flow in the higher permeability inclusion and hence reduced product formation. The *Enhanced Focus* scenario displays the largest enhancement of the scenarios evaluated. Product formation is enhanced by over 40% for the *Enhanced Focus* scenario compared to the base case homogeneous cylinders; this confirms continuum results by Cirpka and Kitanidis [2000] and Werth et al. [2006] which indicate that product enhancement is proportional to the extent flow is focused in higher permeability inclusion. The mixing enhancements measured

in these simulations are in excellent agreement with predicted enhancements based on equation (1). The one difference between equation (1) and the pore-scale modeling results is equation (1) predicts the enhancement occurs within the inclusion while our modeling indicates the enhancement occurs at the down gradient boundary of the flow focusing zone.

FIGURE 5. Effect of reaction rate on product formation is evaluated.

In the preceding example, all reaction rates were set fast such that the effects of mixing could be studied independently of reaction rate. To understand the effects of reaction rate on product formation, we choose one flow scenario, the “middle-long” scenario, and adjusted the reaction rate until conditions became rate limited. Figure 5 shows that for the two highest reaction rates evaluated, product formation profiles are nearly coincident indicating that for reactions faster than $k_{eff} \sim 50 \mu M^{-1} s^{-1}$, the reaction can be treated as instantaneous. As the reaction rate decreases, the effect of the enhanced mixing zone can still be observed (i.e. see profile $k_{eff} = 5 \times 10^{-1} \mu M^{-1} s^{-1}$). At very slow reaction rates, the diffusive supply of substrates significantly exceeds chemical transformation and concentrations become controlled by the reaction rate. Interestingly, for slow reaction rates, the location of the preferential mixing zone does play a role in the overall product formation rate. Specifically, for the slow reaction rate, $k_{eff} = 5 \times 10^{-3} \mu M^{-1} s^{-1}$, the *inlet* mixing scenario has a higher product formation compared to the *middle* mixing scenario. This indicates that for very slow reactions, the earlier substrates experience enhanced mixing, the greater overall product transformation.

3.2. Experimental Results. Micro-model experiments consisting of identical pore structures to LB-FVM simulations were conducted to measure dispersion under experimental

FIGURE 6. Experimental fluorescent image of reactive transport within a micro-model. Flow is from the left to right with the fluorophore OG5N being introduced on the top and Ca being introduced on the bottom. The bright region along the center line is the fluorescent product which is formed from the reaction of OG5N with Ca. Note: porous media structure is completely symmetric about the longitudinal center line and is identical to the LB-FVM network shown in Figure 3.

non-reactive and reactive flow conditions. Figure 6 shows a reactive plume forming under steady laminar flow conditions in a micromodel. On the left hand side, the flow is focused towards the center where a higher conductivity region exists. As the flow leaves the flow focused regime, the plume expands quickly resulting in a corresponding increase in product mass. This effect can be seen conclusively in Figure 4 where mass from the LB-FVM is calculated; as the plume exits the flow focused regime, there is a significant increase in product mass. The micromodel experiment in Figure 6 consists of an identical pore structure to the LB-FVM simulation in Figure 3. The LB-FVM simulation captures the overall behavior of the product formation quite well, including the relative size of the product plume within and down gradient of the enhanced mixing zone. Additional analysis quantifying product formation rates for the micro-model studies, including comparisons with LB-FVM simulations, will be completed in the near future.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study we evaluated the effects of preferential flow focusing on mixing enhancement using pore-scale LB-FVM simulations and experimental micro-model flow cells. Several flow regimes were systematically tested to determine the effects of flow focusing location, length and the intrinsic reaction rate on product formation rates. Results from our study indicate that the extent of reaction for our flow focused scenarios were increased by over 40% compared to identical structures not containing the flow focused region. Simulations evaluating the effect of flow focusing location on extent of product formation demonstrated that the longitudinal location does not have any affect on the overall extent of reaction for fast reactions, but does play a role when reaction rates are limiting. The length of the flow focusing region has a measurable but small effect on the overall extent of product formation. In agreement with previously published continuum studies [Cirpka and Kitanidis, 2000; Werth et al., 2006], our simulations demonstrate

that the larger the relative amount of fluid focused into the inclusion (e.g. the larger the difference in permeability between the inclusion and matrix) the larger the mixing enhancement.

The findings of this study shed light on the factors controlling enhanced mixing within preferential flow zones. Designing mixing strategies which take advantage of enhanced mixing within high permeability zones may provide better solutions for delivery of limiting substrates to contaminant plumes, thereby resulting in more efficient remediation strategies.

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